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T. Mokgohloa
Johannesburg
South Africa

MECHATRONICS DESIGN INSTRUCTION

By

T. Mokgohloa

PROJECT 1:

ASSEMBLY, PROGRAMMING AND COMMISSIONING OF A TURNING STATION

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SCENARIO You are in charge of delivering a turning station that a customer worldwide has ordered to be employed in the production process' partial automation. Work pieces are turned and transported using the method.		A detailed 3D CAD model of a complex industrial turning station. The machine features a central vertical column with a horizontal cross-arm. A rotating table is mounted on the base, with various mechanical components, sensors, and actuators attached. The model is rendered in a clean, technical style with a white background.

TASK

Assemble, wire and tube the production line on the profile plate according to this documentation.

Your task is complete when:

1. The production line has been correctly wired, connected, and physically constructed, and it is guaranteed to operate successfully (based on evaluation using the simulation box).
2. It is guaranteed that the program will be executed correctly with PLC activation (based on examination with PLC).
3. According to the 'Agreement on Professional Practice' that has been distributed separately, the system satisfies the requirements.

As soon as you are done, the customer will receive the system. Later on, you won't have the chance to improve. Hardware issues that arise during the assessment stage can be resolved later. (Worldskills Sao Paulo 2015 Mechatronics test project, 2015)

OPERATION OF THE SYSTEM

Workpieces are pushed from the stacking magazine onto the conveyor belt when the start button is pressed. All black workpieces travel to the end of the conveyor without stopping and goes into the slide. Sliver and red workpieces stop at the measuring module to determine the orientation of the workpiece.

Sliver and red workpieces with the hole side down proceeds and stops at the turning module. Once turned they proceed to the end of the conveyor and falls into the slide. Sliver and red workpieces with the hole side up proceeds from measuring to the end of the conveyor and falls into the slide.

For manual operation, the system run one cycle and stop. The start button will be pressed to start another cycle. On automatic mode, the system run 5 cycles and stop. The system must be restarted to start another cycle.

PRODUCTION LINE LAYOUT

1. Stacking magazine
2. Turning module
3. End Slide
4. Diffuse sensor (measuring): Information about teaching and wiring is in USB stick
5. Reflective sensors
6. Sorting gate
7. Light barrier
8. Tower light

WORKPIECES WILL BE TRANSPORTED TO DIFFERENT POSITIONS ACCORDING TO THE COLOUR AND ORIENTATION.

	HOLESIDE DOWN	HOLESIDE UP	BLACK
Stacking magazine module			
Measuring module	X	X	
Turning module	X		
Slide		X	X

“PLACE ON ...” MEANS:

Wiring additional signals to X7 (pin 5-8 Inputs, pin 13-16 Outputs)

ELECTRICAL INFORMATION - ASSEMBLY AND WIRING OF SIGNAL COLUMN

ELECTRICAL INFORMATION – TURNING STATION MODULES

1.1 DETAILS OF STACKING MAGAZINE MODULE

Wiring allocation on mini-terminal

	PIN on SUB-D	Colour DIN47100	Pin I/O-Mini-Terminal	Function
	1	Purple	0	Magazine empty
	2	Black	1	Eject workpiece
	3	Red	2	Cylinder retracted
	4	-	-	-
	5	White	3	Cylinder extended
	6-11	-	-	-
	12	Yellow	24V	24V
	13	Blue	24V	24V
	14	Green	0V	0V
	15	Brown	0V	0V

Pneumatic circuit diagram

1.2 DETAILS OF TURNING MODULE

Pin allocation for 15-pin Sub-D – Valve Terminal

	PIN	Core colour	Coil	Function
	1	White	0	Turn gripper anti- clockwise
	2	Brown	1	Open gripper
	3	Green	2	Move gripper unit up
	4	Yellow	3	Move gripper unit down
	5-13	-	-	-
	14	Brown-green	-	0V
	15	White-yellow	-	0V

Wiring allocation Multi-pin plug distributor

	PIN on SUB-D	Colour DIN47100	Pin I/O-Mini-Terminal	Function
	1	White	0	Gripper unit is up
	2	Brown	1	Gripper unit is down
	3	Green	2	Gripper is turned clockwise (1B1) (not used)
	4	Yellow	3	Gripper is turned anti-clockwise(1B2)
	5	Grey	4	Gripper is open (not used)
	6	Pink	5	Gripper is closed
	7	Blue	6	Not used
	8	Red	7	Not Used
	9-12	-	-	-
	13	White-green	0-7/ 1	24V
	14	Brown-green	0-7/ 3	0V
	15	White-yellow	0-7/ 3	0V

Pneumatic circuit diagram

WIRING OF INPUTS AND OUTPUTS ON TURNING STATION: I/O TERMINAL

Connector I/O terminal	Description		
Inputs			
DI0	Reflective sensor: workpieces at the beginning of the conveyor		
DI1	Reflective sensor: silver and red workpieces at the measuring position		
DI2	Diffuse sensor: orientation of the silver and red workpieces		
DI3	Reflective sensor: silver and red workpieces at the turning module		
DI4	Light barrier sensor: workpieces at the end of the conveyor/ slide full		
DI5	Magazine cylinder retracted (1B1)		
DI6	Light barrier on magazine (magazine empty)		
DI7	Magazine cylinder extended (1B2)		
Outputs			
DQ0	Conveyor belt runs forward		
DQ1	Extend Sorting gate		
DQ2	Extend magazine cylinder		
DQ3	Green tower light		
DQ4	Orange tower light		
DQ5	Red tower light		
DQ6	Not used		
DQ7	Not used		
Total score:			

1.1 WIRING OF INPUTS AND OUTPUTS ON TURNING STATION: CONTROL PANEL

Control panel: turning module	Description		
Inputs			
DI0 – 3	Used by Control panel		
DI4	Gripper unit up position		
DI5	Gripper unit down position		

DI6	Gripper unit turned anti-clockwise (1B2)		
DI7	Gripper is closed		
Outputs			
DQ0 – 3	Used by Control panel		
DQ4	Turn gripper		
DQ5	Open gripper		
DQ6	Move gripper unit up (extend)		
DQ7	Move gripper unit down (retract)		

Works Cited

Worldskills Sao Paulo 2015 Mechatronics test project. (2015). Retrieved from <https://worldskills.org/>: <https://worldskills.org/>